

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STRESS AND DEPRESSION

UNIVERSITY OF GHANA, LEGON

FACULTY OF SOCIAL SCIENCES

DEPARTMENT OF PSYCHOLOGY

**ASSOCIATIONS BETWEEN LEVEL OF STRESS AND DEPRESSION AMONG
STUDENTS**

BY

JONES MARK AHIATI

(10681957)

SUPERVISOR: DR. ADOTE ANUM

ABSTRACT

This research study examined the level of stress and depression associated with students and how social support influences the stress and depression levels of students. There are several interactions between stress, depression, and social support towards the well-being of students at the tertiary level. One hundred students from Legon Hall of the University of Ghana were included in the research study; there were 50 males and 50 females who voluntarily took part in the filling of questionnaires relating to the Perceived Stress Scale, Beck Depression Scale, and Appraisal Support Subscale. The study was conducted using a cross-sectional study to assess the participants' level of stress, level of depression, and social support level. The result of the study showed that there was a significant difference in the level of stress among male and female students, in that males tend to have a higher level of stress than females. Also, depression accounted for a significant difference between males and females. Moreover, stress and depression accounted for a statistically significant difference, such that the high level of stress accounted for a high level of depression among participants. Also, social support and depression accounted for a statistically significant difference, but there was no statistically significant difference between social support and stress. The findings showed that students are easily associated with stress challenges, and the high level of stress was identified to cause health problems, such as high depression.

DEDICATION

This research work is dedicated to my parents, brothers, and all those who supported me throughout my undergraduate studies. I am very grateful for all the supports, encouragement, and motivation I had from my parents, brothers, and the University of Ghana. I appreciate everything that was given to support my education.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

My utmost thanks to God for helping me complete this research work successfully. I will like to show my appreciation to all the students who dedicated their time and efforts to complete the questionnaire to provide data for the research study. Many thanks to my supervisor Dr. Adote Anum to all the guidance, patience, comments and suggestions throughout the entire process of my research project. I really got enough insight with your training and suggestions to undertake the research work, thanks a lot for all your help. My thanks to the lecturers of the Department of Psychology of the University of Ghana for all their training and supports throughout my Undergraduate studies at the University of Ghana. Finally, I will like to express my appreciation to Mr. Akrong Newton for his advice and guidance when there was no one to respond to my queries. My thanks to my parents Mr. George Ahiati and Mrs. Peace Ahiati for all their prayers, supports, and encouragement. Thank you!

TABLE OF CONTENT

	PAGES
LIST OF TABLES.....	vii
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS.....	viii
CHAPTER ONE.....	1
Introduction.....	1
Background to the Study.....	1
Aims and Objectives of the Study.....	3
Relevance of the Study.....	4
CHAPTER TWO.....	5
Review of Literature.....	5
Theoretical Framework.....	5
Review of Related Literature.....	7
Rationale of the Study.....	12
Statement of Hypothesis.....	12
CHAPTER THREE.....	13
Methodology.....	13
Population.....	13

Sample and Sampling Technique.....	13
The Selection Criteria.....	14
Measures.....	14
Design.....	15
Procedure.....	15
Analysis of Data.....	16
CHAPTER FOUR.....	17
Introduction.....	17
Data Collection.....	17
Demographic Analysis.....	19
Hypothesis Testing.....	21
CHAPTER FIVE.....	26
Introduction.....	26
Discussion of Findings.....	26
Implications for Future Research.....	30
Limitations of the Research Study.....	30
Conclusion.....	31

REFERENCES.....	32
APPENDIX A.....	36
Demographic Questionnaire.....	36
APPENDIX B.....	37
Perceived Stress Scale.....	37
APPENDIX C.....	38
Beck's Depression Inventory.....	38
APPENDIX D.....	41
Social Support Scale.....	41

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Gender Demographic characteristics of participants.....	19
Table 2: Activities Demographic characteristics of participants.....	20
Table 3: Summary of Table of Means, Standard deviations and p-value.....	20
Table 4: Independent Sample Test Analysis for Hypothesis One.....	22
Table 4: Independent Sample Test Analysis for Hypotheses Two.....	23
Table 5: ANOVA Analysis for Hypothesis Three.....	24
Table 6: ANOVA Analysis for Hypothesis Four.....	25

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

BDI	Beck Depression Inventory
PSS	Perceived Stress Scale
SSS	Social Support Scale

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Background

Stress is one of the most discussed topics in the field of health and wellbeing among individuals. The problem of stress is a major health challenge among people in several countries today (O'Connor, et al., 2021). Stress is concerned with emotional and physical tension associated with external events and pressure (Monroe & Reid, 2009). The problem of stress can be sourced from a variety of factors, these are ranged from social factors, biological factors, environmental factors, behavioral factors, health factors, among many other factors (Schneiderman, et al., 2005). The persistent stress over a period of time can bring about depression and other chronic illnesses (Yang, et al. 2015). Depression is a health problem that affects the body processes including the mood, mental state, appetite, sleep, and the feeling of an individual (Tiller, 2013).

The social factors of stress project the interaction of people with society. The interaction and activities of people towards wealth, performing religious practices, engaging in continuous buying, the level of education, the size range of a family, the structure of an individual's family, and the level of the population (Bartolomucci, et al., 2005). The level of stress is often related to the social life of people. When there is too much workload on a person, it can cause stress and this may reduce the level of interaction with friends. They turn to be irritable, unfriendly, and hostile and the problem of stress can be traced to the micro-environment (the family or friends) and the macro-environment (Kessler, et al., 1985). Social stress is a very common stressor that is experienced by most people each and every day and is known to be the most intense stressor to people than any other stressor (Bartolomucci, et al., 2005). The social stress theory according to

Thoits, (1999) states that social factors can contribute to illness among individuals and disturb the bring about unhealthy conditions.

Biological factors to stress can be related to the nervous system activation and both neuroendocrine axes that interact with the brain, various hormones, and glands to help human response to various environmental stimuli and biological changes during conditions like stress (Bremner & Vermetten, 2001). The Autonomic Nervous System often provides the responses to stress, the subdivisions perform roles in responding to stress. The Sympathetic Nervous System responds with the fight or flight attribute. This happens when the body provides enough energy resources in order to prevent threats to the body. The Sympathetic Nervous System propels the adrenal glands in releasing adrenalin or epinephrine and cortisol. The adrenalin hormone improves the level of heart rate, blood pressure, and energy for the body. The cortisol is a stress hormone that helps in facilitating the level of sugar or glucose in the blood and improves improve the use of glucose in the blood to aid in the repair of tissues (Yehuda, 1999). Also, the Parasympathetic Nervous System will help decrease the heart rate and maintaining homeostasis of the body, it provides a break and rest to the body. The sympathetic arousal and hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenocortical axis activation relate directly to stress. The high physical interaction with the level of homeostasis can lead to stress and changes in the equilibrium level in the body (Bremner & Vermetten, 2001).

Health factors can propel stress and induce varied health situations in the long run. Chronic illness is a health problem that can relate to stress. The problem of illness can hinder the normal functioning of the body, this can increase the level of emotional tension and relation with the environment (Weigel & Shrout, 2020). Health compromising conditions can factor into stress, emotional problems like anxiety, anger, low self-esteem, depression and weakness will gradually

decrease the wellbeing of the individual. The occurrence of disasters, terrible events, and situations can factor into the stress level of people (Palgi et al., 2019).

The behavior of people can also factor into stress, the mediating behavior can range from smoking, drug use, tobacco use, alcohol addicted behavior, and the attitude of individual can contribute to the stress level (Neumark-Sztainer et al., 1997). The behavior of people can account for the stress level and emotions of low strength. Several people turn to withdraw from work and society due to behavioral interaction to the wellbeing of the individual. The behavior of people can easily be attributed to exposure to extreme stressors. The behavior of alcohol or drug usage and tobacco usage can propel the level of depression. The level of stress and depression is common among university students due to the different behaviors and activities performed during the university period (Simantov, et al., 2000).

Aims or objectives

The study is aimed at examining the association between stress and depression by researching the influence of male and female students' levels of stress that may elicit depression. The study is aimed at;

1. To examine the relationship between stress and depression
2. To investigate gender differences in stress
3. To investigate gender differences in depression

The relevance of the Study

The research will provide the problems associated with students dealing with stress and depression. This will bring to light the behaviors that contribute to stress and related problems. These problems will help educate students and the public on how to go about activities and avoid those actions that can easily be associated with stress, especially during school periods. The study will help inform school counselors and psychologists about the level of stress that can propel the unhealthy conditions among students at the university level and how to manage and deal with students with stress conditions. The study will also be relevant to professionals in health to know the measure to undertake to enhance the wellbeing of students in the university. This research will be able to encourage students to seek help from counselors and psychologists to guide them improve their psychological wellbeing and the effect will enable them to deal with health-related problems and behaviors that can elicit stress. This will also help students to trust counselors and psychologists for supports and guide during stress periods. The finding from the studies will help improve the level of care and attention towards dealing with stress and depression.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Theoretical Framework

Biological diathesis stress model of depression (Ingram and Luxton, 2005)

The stress model has factors that lead to depression and other psychological disorders among males and females. Psychologists have identified factors relating to cognitive performance, depression, anxiety, and other psychological disorders are induced by exposure to stress (Ingram and Luxton, 2005). Stressful events can highly cause depression in the behavior of people even without biological influence. People encounter different levels of stress each and every day, the predominant exposure to stress can easily put the psychological health of the person at high risk. Biological diathesis theory has a link between the medical history, health condition, and biological or physiological state of a person in relation to the psychological effect of these factors. Health conditions can easily trigger stress among patients, most people with medical conditions are given psychological interventions to minimize psychological problems, stress, and other related problems. Schizophrenic patients have predominant exposure and risk to stress and the diathesis-stress model was used to understand the association between stress and other problems like depression (Ingram and Luxton, 2005). The model of depression ranges from stress exposure, having events and conditions associated with stress can easily make a person susceptible to depression. People are less likely to determine the occurrence of events or situations in the real world, situations like natural disasters, unemployment, conflicts, among other conditions. There are several events that result in stress in society, prolong exposure to stress can easily result in depression. Independent situations are not controlled by individuals like

natural disasters, while dependent stress factors can be linked to a person's way of life such as smoking, quarreling, and drug abuse. The biological diathesis-stress model is an empirical theory that shows that psychological disorders like depression can result from the biological state of a person in association with stress.

Stress generation theory in association with depression (Morgan, Dell'Isola, Nicholson & Spencer, 2020)

Stress generation theory is more about how people encounter stress and the effect of stress on their health. The theory started when researchers were studying depression among women and how easily life stressors can be encountered among women. Depression can be a continuous intriguing factor to stress, people who have depression symptoms are often engaging in events and behaviors that result in more stress. Depression usually increases the burden of unhealthy living among individuals having depression symptoms, people suffer stressful relationships, communicating problems, and health-compromising behaviors. The study of the stress generation theory showed that people with stress and depression often engage in varying levels of conflict. Most couples do not live a happy life in their relationships when at least one has symptoms of stress. There is a prevalence of conflict and risky stressful practices among couples having depression symptoms. Stress generation theory has opened the understanding of the risks associated with depression especially among couples and relationships, people focus on associating with threatening practices that destroy relationships.

Cognitive theory of major depression (Ellis, 1987)

The theory of major depression pointed that the cognitive aspect of a person can take the physical interaction of a person, the irrational beliefs and thoughts of someone can actually

control the behavior of the person. People seeing themselves as worthless, irrelevant, can result in more stressful and harmful behaviors that increase psychological problems. Thinking can take a physical form to control the behavior of a person, (Ellis, 1987) showed that people make wrong demands on themselves or others based on their thoughts, depressive thinking causes individuals to result in unproductive acts. Ellis identified biases among individual's understanding of external events and information. People often ignore good information and focus more on wrong, bad, and unhealthy information, the ideas some students use such as not getting the expected grade and thinking subsequent performance will be like the previous score. This can discourage students and hinder their potential of scoring better grades in subsequent tests.

Review of Related Literature

There are several studies that have been done on stress, depression, and how they are connected among people. The following review shows some of the studies done on the relationship between stress and depression among different individuals in different places.

Studies Conducted

Studies conducted on the relationship between stress level and depression among students showed a positive correlation, the higher the stress of students, there is a high chance of depression (Das & Sahoo, 2012). The level of stress between men and women varies, most females are vulnerable to stress and depression than males (Gore et al., 2010). Students in the University mostly face stress related problem (Saleh et al., 2017). Females usually show higher pains and anxiety than males (Matud, 2004). Studies also show that males are easy to cope with stress better than females. The males are mostly problem-focused and often engage in activities

to deal with problems as compared to females (Ptacek et al., 1994). The study done on the effect of a disease outbreak on the level of stress among males and females showed that females are vulnerable to stress and psychological disorders than males (Hou et al., 2020). The study of other research shows no difference in the gender relationship with stress and depression among workers (Felsten, 2007). There was research done among workers that also showed that men engage in more work and are mostly associated with high stress as compared to women at work (Wege et al., 2018). At home and school, females turn to be more focused on dealing with problems and coping than males (Sigmon et al., 2007). Males are easier to deal with stress as compared to females, also, males are able to express low anxiety and depression than female but there is no level of stress associated with depression among males and females from health-compromising behaviors such as too much smoking or drug use (Fox & Sinha, 2009).

Gender differences of depression and anxiety among social media users in China

A cross-sectional study was conducted in China among different genders. Participants completed questions related to social demography and COVID-19, Patient Health Questionnaire, Generalized Anxiety Disorder Scale and Connor-Davidson Scale. Stress has varied relations to depression, the level of stress can be acute, chronic, or varied. Hou et al., (2020) investigated stress among males and females during the outbreak of infectious diseases like COVID-19. Females were mostly experiencing a variety of psychological problems including a high level of stress as compared to males. The level of depression among males and females varied, the studies were done in China, participants were about 3088, gotten from social media groups, they were presented with Patient Health Questionnaire and other psychological scales to gather data relating to the psychological states of these participants during the outbreak of infectious disease. The data collected were analyzed using the ANOVA test, the result from the study showed that

there was some level of depression and anxiety among both genders during the outbreak of infectious disease. More so, females were experiencing a high level of stress, depression, and anxiety symptoms, but males were very resilient and endurance to stress. From the studies, the level of depression decreases as participants age and resilience increases, but depression is higher as age and resilience decrease. People with problems like unemployment, low adaptation, and stressful life are more depressed as compared to those who are employed, able to adapt, and less stressed. The research was able to help improve the lifestyle of the Chinese population during the outbreak of COVID-19 to get enough relevant information and resources for a healthier living.

Academic Stress and Social Support on Psychological Wellbeing of Adolescents

Glozah, (2013) research study which was conducted among some adolescents in Ghana, getting the understanding into how academic stress affect the psychological health of students in the Senior High School-level in Ghana, and the influence of perceived social support on student's psychological wellbeing. Participants were both males and females, (males and females = 226, males = 131, females = 95; age range was between 13 to 22). Questionnaires were given randomly and students were selected randomly depending on those who wished to take part in the test. The research test was conducted by using student life stress inventory, general health questionnaire, and perceived social support from family and friend's scales. These tests measured the level of stress, psychological health, and supports from families and friends. Social support reduced the impact of academic stress, girls had a high level of depression along with high social supports. Boys had high academic stress, high socialization, good psychological health, and healthy interpersonal relationships. Adolescents are easily prone to stress especially in the academic environment, males turn to be more sociable than females, which makes it possible for males to manage their stress properly. Females result in unsatisfactory social

supports and relationships, increasing their stress level, resulting in depression, and reducing their psychological wellbeing. Social support can highly improve the psychological well-being of students and improve their academic performance.

Social support can be from several individuals or sources, these make them either formal and informal, the relationship with friends, work partners, and family can be informal, but a relationship with a psychologist, doctor, lecturer, and a counselor will be formal. These types of relationships provide social support to individuals, enabling them to minimize the adverse effects of stress on their health. The test was also done to determine the influence of the socio-economic status of each participant, the educational level of participants' parents, and how it affects the psychological wellbeing of various students. The two-way analysis of covariance was used to analyze the influence of various factors on the wellbeing of participants. One-way or two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and t-test was used to identify the group difference in the various tests. The result showed that social support was actually relevant in the psychological wellness of students. There was more support for students with parents who had higher educations as compared to students with parents with a low level of education, this links to the difference in psychological wellbeing among students depending on the level of education of their parents.

The relationship between adolescent stress and anxiety and depression symptoms.

Anyan & Hjemdal, (2016) researched the exposure to stress among adolescents, the resilience to stress among individuals can relate to the level of depression and anxiety symptoms among adolescents. The study was a cross-sectional survey conducted on Ghanaian adolescents; the total participants were 533 between the ages of 13 to 17 respectively. Participants consisted of girls = 290; boys = 237, and they were given the Resilience Scale for Adolescents, Adolescent

Stress Questionnaire, the Spielberger State Anxiety Inventory, and Short Mood Feeling Questionnaire. The test was analyzed by the mediation and moderation analysis. The result from the research study showed that there was some influence of resilience on the relationship between stress and depression and anxiety symptoms. The higher the resilience level to stress, the lower the effect of stress, when the stress level is high, the result can increase the level of depression and anxiety symptoms among adolescents. The resilience of adolescents to stress can help reduce depression levels but not improve the level of anxiety. Adolescents who are able to resist stress and minimize stress are able to improve their psychological wellbeing and reduce depression and other psychological health problems.

The relationship between perceived stress and depression among college students

Skipworth, (2011) researched the relationship between stress and depression among some college students, the study showed that the level of stress among college students is very high, the fresh students hardly manage their stress and leads to health challenges. The research was conducted using a retrospective cross-sectional correlation technique, this design was able to identify the relationship between stress, personal activities, and health-related conditions like stress among various participants. There were more females than males, (females = 580; males = 483) with an average age of 23, selected from the student population in Arizona State University. The participants completed the American Health Association-National College Health Assessment (ACHA-NCHA). The analysis was done and showed that there was a significant relationship between stress and depression among college students.

The rationale for the Study

There are several kinds of research that have been done on stress, depression, and the relationship between stress and depression among different groups of people in different countries. Several of these researches focus on depression as an effect of stress among students. Several of these researches also show that depression results only when the level of stress is very high among students. Other researches show that females are more easily get depressed as compared to males. Several studies have ignored the influence of gender difference in behavioral factors that can put students at risk to a highly depressed state along with stress. Several kinds of research have also avoided the prevalence of stress among males as compared to females, male students often engage in several activities that associate them with stress than females. Other researchers have ignored the fact that females mostly engage in less stressful activities and relax mostly than males, which makes female students experience less stress than males. This study aims at examining the various ways gender differences associate with the relationship between stress and depression among university students.

Statement of Hypothesis

There are some hypotheses formulated relating to the theories and reviewed studies conducted;

1. The level of stress will be very high among male students as compared to female students in the University.
2. Males will have significantly higher levels of depression than females.
3. Students with high level of stress will have high level of depression.
4. Students with high social support will have lower level of stress and depression.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

The methodology provides an overview of the various settings for the research, the description of the population of the research, the respondents used for the research, the selection method used to select the respondents or participants, and the various rationales, measures, and techniques used for the research.

Population

Students at the University of Ghana were selected as participants for the research study. This population was chosen because students in the University are exposed to a variety of stressful conditions that cause depression. The population of students from the University is made up of different age groups and degree levels. The population consists of Undergraduates, Postgraduates, and even Diploma students. The student population in the University consists of both males and females who can take part in the research study. The population is made up of over 40,000 students and this research is limited to the undergraduate student population in Legon Hall of the University of Ghana.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sampling frame for the research was the student's population in Legon Hall of the University of Ghana. The student population in Legon Hall at the University of Ghana will be around 2,000 students and beyond. The sampling technique used was the random sampling of 100 students selected from the student population of Legon Hall in the University of Ghana. The

students selected are made up of both males and females with equal chances of being selected depending on their agreement to take part as participants in the research study. The students were given questionnaires to fill relating to psychological wellbeing, stress, and depression. Both males and females filled the same questionnaires related to stress and depression.

The Selection Criteria

- I. The research study was directed to students between the ages of 17 and 28, since several of the students will fall between this age range.
- II. Students who are currently in the academic semester were used for the research; this will propel stress among the student participants for the study.
- III. Students selected are residents of Legon Hall and not any other student hall on the University campus.
- IV. Students who did not agree to participate in the research were excluded from the research study.

Measures

The level of stress variable of participants includes the high level of stress, minimal stress, low-stress level among other levels is generated from self-report questionnaires.

The depression test scale will be used to collect data relating to the health condition of participants and how the level of stress will affect the psychological wellbeing of participants.

The instrument used to measure the stress level of participants will be the perceived stress scale. The perceived stress scale can examine the feeling, thought, behavior, and experiences of participants. The test is able to assess the relationship between the participants and the environment, how they deal with stressors, and the coping strategies of both genders. This instrument for measuring stress is able to measure factors that can be examined as stress in participants' life. The instrument for the measurement of depression is the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), is a self-report test in a form of a questionnaire.

Design

The research is done to understand and examine the relationship between the level of stress and depression among male and female students in the University of Ghana. The research design to be used is a cross-sectional research design, this is because the research is aimed at knowing how males and females encounter stress, the level of stress among both genders, and the relation between the level of stress and depression. This is also because there is no manipulation of variables, participants received questionnaires which were used to generate data about the stress level, gender, and depression among students in the University.

Procedure

The student participants were given a questionnaire to fill, students who agreed to participate were included. The consent to participate was taken from each student who participated in the research study. The questionnaires were distributed to the students in the respective hall which is Legon Hall in the University of Ghana. Incentives were used to attract some students to participate in the research. Students filled the questionnaires in their various rooms. Males and

females were separated in the hall, both genders were in a separate environment in the same hall. Students were assisted during the answering of questionnaires. The questionnaires were given to participants individually. The researcher was present during the filling of the questionnaires by various participants.

Ethical Consideration was used during the research study, participants privacy was observed, the various psychological ethical codes were observed. There was voluntarism, participant compensation, confidentiality observation, and protection of individual rights.

Analysis of Data

The analysis of data was done by the use of SPSS software, the various hypothesis was analyzed using the independent sample t-test and One-Way ANOVA. The various data were coded directly into the SPSS for Windows, version 20. The unneeded data were excluded and the needed data was used. The responses of the data collected were grouped into a simpler form (such as low, moderate, and high level). The statistical frequencies we conducted to identify the relationship between various variables. The independent and dependent variables were analyzed to examine the relationship between both variables.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

Introduction

The focus of this chapter is directed to the analysis of data collected from participants of the research study. The research study was aimed at examining the relationship between stress and depression among students, gender differences in stress, and investigate gender differences in depression. Statistical tests and analysis were conducted to identify the findings from the research conducted among the various participants.

Data Collection

The responses from 100 students from Legon Hall in the University of Ghana were coded and recorded into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS for Windows, version 20). The participants were made up of 50 males, and 50 females respectively. The students were undergraduates between the ages of 17 and 28 years respectively. The data were arranged according to the relevant scales for the research, the perceived stress scale, beck depression inventory, and the social support subscale was used, only relevant questions from the social support scale were used to collect social support data from the participants. The perceived stress scale was coded from 0 to 4 (0 = never, 1 = almost never, 2 = sometimes, 3 = fairly often, 4 = very often). There was a reverse scoring of questions 4, 5, 7, and 8, in the form of 0 = 4, 1 = 3, 2 = 2, 3 = 1, and 4 = 0. The sum of perceived stress score for each participant was recorded and the score was ranged from 0 to 40 in such that, score range of 0 to 13 was considered as low stress, score range of 14 to 26 was considered moderate stress, and a score range of 27 to 40 was

considered high perceived stress. From the analysis, 12 participants had low perceived stress, 75 participants had moderate stress, and 13 participants had high perceived stress.

The Beck Depression Inventory scale was coded from 0 to 3 in such that 0 shows not experiencing a condition, 1 showing less experience of a condition, 2 meaning almost experiencing a condition, 3 means highly experiencing a condition directed to having depression. The total score of each Participants were ranged from 0 to 63, the lowest score was 0 signifying no depression. The range of 1 to 10 shows minimal depression, 11 to 16 shows mild depression, 17 to 20 shows borderline depression, 21 to 30 shows moderate depression, 31 to 40 shows severe depression, and above 40 score shows extreme depression. From the analysis, 8 participants had no depression, 49 participants had minimal depression, 18 participants had mild depression, 4 participants had borderline depression, 11 participants had moderate depression, and 10 participants had severe depression.

The Appraisal Support subscale for Social Support was comprising of items 2, 4, 6, and 11 of the Interpersonal Support Evaluation List. Item 2 and item 11 were reverse scored in such that items; 1 = 4, 2 = 3, 3 = 2, 4 = 1 respectively. The coding was score based on 1 to 4; 1 means definitely false, 2 means probably false, 3 means probably true, and 4 means definitely true. The total score for each participant was recorded from the range of 4 to 16; such that range of 4 to 8 means low social support, 9 to 11 is minimal social support, and 12 to 16 is high social support. From the analysis, 20 participants had low social support, 33 participants had minimal social support, and 47 participants had high social support.

Demographic analysis

The participants were made up of 50 males, and 50 females respectively as shown in Table 1, Frequency and descriptive analysis of the demographic characteristic was conducted and the gender mean was 1.5, mean age was 20.17, SD of age was 1.97. Mean of Perceived Stress Score (PSS) was 19.27 (SD = 6.08), Mean of Beck Depression Inventory Score was 12.30 (SD = 10.51), and the Mean Social Support Score was 11.20 (SD = 3.41).

Table 1: Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	50	50.0	50.0	50.0
Female	50	50.0	50.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

98% of the participants were single, 1% of the participants was married, and 1% of the participants was in some kind of casual relationship. The participants were affiliated to different religious groups, 35% of the participants were Orthodox Christians, 32% of the participants were Pentecostal Christians, 27% of the participants were Charismatic Christians, 2% of the participants were Muslims, 4% of the participants were not in any of the above denominations. The level of participants was classified as 69% of the total participants were level 100 students, 6% of the participants were level 200 students, 5% of the participants were in level 300 and 20% of the participants were in level 400. In activities, 25% of the participants took part in sports, 32% of the participant took part in singing, 8% of the participants took part in student leadership activities, with other activities comprising 4% (comedy, dancing, drumming, and writing activities), and 31% of the participants did not take part in any activities as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Activities

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Sport	25	25.0	25.0	25.0
Singing	32	32.0	32.0	57.0
Stud. Leadership	8	8.0	8.0	65.0
Other activities	4	4.0	4.0	69.0
None	31	31.0	31.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

The summary of mean, standard deviation and p-value of gender in relation to the PSS (Perceived Stress Scale), BDI (Beck Depression Inventory) and SSS (Social Support Scale) among participants in Table 3.

Table 3: Mean, Standard Deviation, and p-value

Variables	N	Mean	Standard D.	P-value
PSS:	Male	17.62	5.80	.006
	Female	20.92	5.97	
BDI	Male	8.84	9.02	.001
	Female	15.76	10.85	
SSS	Male	11.42	3.12	.522
	Female	10.98	3.70	

Significant difference between means p-value < 0.05

The mean of PSS among male participants is 17.62 (SD=5.80), and mean of PSS among female participants is 20.92 (SD=5.97), suggesting that female participants have high perceived stress

and compared to males. The mean of BDI among male participants is 8.84 (SD=9.02), and mean of BDI among female participants is 15.76 (SD=10.85), suggesting that females have high depression as compared to male participants. The mean of SSS among male participants is 11.42 (SD=3.12), suggesting that male participants have high social supports as compared to female participants having SSS mean of 10.98 (SD=3.7).

Hypothesis 1

The first hypothesis was that “the level of stress will be very high among male students as compared to female students in the University.” Analyzing this hypothesis, an independent sample t-test was computed to find the relationship between the level of stress between male and female participants. The results are shown in Table 4, 5, and 6.

Table 4: Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means	
		F	Sig.	t	df
PSS and Gender	Equal variances assumed	.106	.745	-2.806	98
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.806	97.918

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
PSS and Gender	Equal variances assumed	.006	-3.30000	1.17620
	Equal variances not assumed	.006	-3.30000	1.17620

Table 5: Independent Samples Test

Table 6: Independent Samples Test

		t-test for Equality of Means	
		95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		Lower	Upper
PSS and Gender	Equal variances assumed	-5.63414	-.96586
	Equal variances not assumed	-5.63416	-.96584

PSS=Perceived Stress Scale, Significant difference between means, p-value < 0.05

From the Independent Sample t-test analysis, there was an equal variance assumed from the levene's test of equality of variances ($F=.106$ and $\text{sig.} = .745$), the t-test of the analysis showed a two-tailed significant difference of .006, since the p-value is less than .05, hence, the first hypothesis stating that "the level of stress will be very high among male students as compared to female students in the University" is accepted, and rejecting the null hypothesis.

Hypothesis 2

The second hypothesis was that “Males will have significantly higher levels of depression than females.” Independent Sample t-test analysis was used to test whether males have high significant level of depression than females. The results of the analysis are shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Independent Samples Test

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
BDI and Gender	Equal variances assumed	.001	-6.92000	1.99447
	Equal variances not assumed	.001	-6.92000	1.99447

BDI=Beck Depression Inventory, Statistical significance different between mean is $p < 0.05$

From the Independent Samples t-test analysis, the statistically significant p-value in 2-tailed is .001, this means the p-value is less than .05, therefore, the second hypothesis is accepted. There is a statistically significant difference between males and females in regards to the level of depression. There is a presumption that female participants have high depression level as compared to male participants.

Hypothesis 3

The third hypothesis stating that “Students with high level of stress will have high level of depression” was analyzed using one-way ANOVA test. This was done to determine whether there is a significant difference between the level of stress and depression among the participants. The results of the analysis are shown in the Table 8.

Table 8: ANOVA for Relationship between PSS and BDI

BDI and PSS

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	4465.486	27	165.388	1.838	.022
Within Groups	6477.514	72	89.965		
Total	10943.000	99			

BDI=Beck Depression Inventory, PSS=Perceived Stress Scale, Statistically Significant differences between means (p-value < 0.05).

From the One-Way ANOVA test analysis, the statistically significant p-value is .022, this means the p-value is less than .05, therefore, the third hypothesis is accepted, therefore, there is a statistically significant difference between PSS and BDI among Students. This shows that the hypothesis is valid and therefore, the null hypothesis can be rejected.

Hypothesis 4

The hypothesis that was stated that “Students with high social support will have lower level of stress and depression” was analyzed using the One-Way ANOVA test. The results of the analysis are shown in Table 9.

Table 9: ANOVA of BDI and PSS by SSS score

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
BDI and SSS	Between Groups	2685.719	12	223.810	2.358	.011
	Within Groups	8257.281	87	94.911		
	Total	10943.000	99			
PSS and SSS	Between Groups	534.568	12	44.547	1.239	.270
	Within Groups	3127.142	87	35.944		
	Total	3661.710	99			

BDI=Beck Depression Inventory, PSS=Perceived Stress Scale, SSS=Social Support Scale, Statistically Significant differences between means (p-value < 0.05).

From the analysis, there was a significant p-value of .011 between BDI and SSS, and a significant p-value of .270 between PSS and SSS. This means that, there is a statistically significant difference between depression and social support (p-value < .05), there is no statistically significant difference between PSS and SSS, since the p-value is greater than .05 (p-value > .05). From this, the hypothesis that students with high level of social support will have lower level of depression is accepted since the p-value < .05, but the hypothesis that, students with high level of social support will have low level of stress is rejected since the p-value between social support and perceived stress is above .05 (p-value > .05).

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSION

Introduction

The research was aimed at determining the association between the levels of stress and depression among both male and female students at the University of Ghana. The descriptive statistics were used to analyze demographic data of the participants, independent t-test and One-Way ANOVA test was used to analyze various hypotheses. It was hypothesized that the level of stress will be very high among male students as compared to female students in the University, Males will have significantly higher levels of depression than females, Students with a high level of stress will have a high level of depression, and Students with high social support will have a lower level of stress and depression. The hypothesis formulated was used to test the aims and objectives of the research under study. This chapter is composed to examine the results, implication of findings, recommendations, and research limitations.

The Level of Stress will be very high among Male Students as compared to Female Students

The result of this hypothesis showed that the level of stress among male participants is different as compared to female participants. The high mean score of females with perceived stress showed that females can be assumed to have high stress as compared to male participants. The relationship demonstrates that females are highly at risk to stress and they experience stress commonly as compared to male students. The outcome of the result implies that female students are often engaged in activities that propel stress conditions to their health. As conducted by previous researchers, females usually show higher pains and anxiety than males (Matud, 2004).

Studies also show that males are easy to cope with stress better than females. The males are mostly problem-focused and often engage in activities to deal with problems as compared to females (Ptacek et al., 1994). This can be used to support the finding of high stress among females as compared to males. The outcome of the study is aligned with previous findings that reported a high level of stress among females. Also, a high level of academic activities and pressures can be an inducing factor to a high level of stress among females, the males are able to cope well with high pressures as compared to females. Female students are not able to cope well with high academic pressures and tasks, this brings about high stress among female students.

Males will have significantly higher levels of depression than Females

The result for the analysis to test for the significant difference between depression levels among males and females showed that there was a significant difference between levels of depression among males and females. Independent Sample t-test was used to analyze the hypothesis to determine the difference between males and females with depression. The analysis showed a high mean value for females with depression as compared to male students with depression referencing from Table 4 in the result.

Female students are assumed to have a high level of depression as compared to male students. The outcome of the result shows that female students are easily associated with depression challenges than males in the University. The association between females and depression can be linked to the high social problems, implications of high academic stress, among other burdens, as stated in previous researches conducted (Hou et al., 2020). More so, females are easily depressed since they have low resilience and endurance to stressful conditions. From the previous studies, depression level increases as a person's resilience level decreases, the influence of chaos, social

problems, and stressful events increases the risk of depression among females. The study conducted by Anyan & Hjemdal, (2016) showed that the resilience level of females is lower than males, this can be used to support the result of high depression among females than males in this current study. The outcome of the research also shows that females do not engage in coping strategies to reduce health-related challenges as compared to males. The use of good coping strategies among students in the Universities will be able to help decrease the depression level of students and enhance their psychological wellbeing.

Students with High Level of Stress will have High Level of Depression

The study also hypothesized that higher stress levels will induce higher depression level, this was tested using the One-Way ANOVA test method, the result of the analysis showed that there was a statistically significance difference, meaning an increase in perceived stress level will cause an increase in depression levels among students in the University. From the finding of the analysis conducted, there is a direct relationship between stress and depression, this can be related to the biological diathesis-stress model of depression (Ingram and Luxton, 2005). Stressful events can highly cause depression in the behavior of people even without biological influence. Students encounter different levels of stress each and every day, the predominant exposure to stress can easily put the psychological health of the person at high risk.

There are several stressors in the environment, some of these stressors are not under the control of students, while others are under the control of students. Some students try to deal with stress by engaging in health-compromising behaviors such as drinking alcohol and eventually triggers depression. The study conducted by Morgan et al., (2020) showed the significance of stress generation theory on the health of people living with stress. The research conducted can support

the finding that depression can increase as stress level increase among students. Depression can be a continuous intriguing factor to stress, people who have depression symptoms are often engaging in events and behaviors that result in more stress. The finding from the research is consistent and supported by previous related studies, this shows how bad stress can affect students in different ways. Students who engage in smoking, drinking alcohol, low exercise, and other stress-inducing behaviors are highly exposed to prolong stress and this can result in severe health challenges like depression.

Students with High Social Support will have Lower Level of Stress and Depression

This hypothesis was analyzed using the One-Way ANOVA test and the result showed that there is a significant difference between depression and social support among students, but there is no significant difference between stress and social support among students. From this analysis, there is a support that students with a high level of social support will have a lower level of depression, but the level of social support does not have any different level of stress among students in the University. Students who have high social support will not influence their stress level since they definitely take part in stressful academic activities along with other stressful endeavors. This means students with high or low social support will still, be facing stress conditions. Students who have high social support will be able to manage stress better than students who do not have high social support. This is the reason why high social support will account for low depression while low social support will account for high depression among students. Cognitive theory of major depression by Ellis, (1987) cognitive aspect of a person can take the physical interaction of a person, the irrational beliefs and thoughts of someone can actually control the behavior of the

person. People who do not have high social support can see themselves as worthless, irrelevant, among other stressful thoughts, this can result in more stressful and harmful behaviors that increase psychological problems. The issue of social support for students is very important since it has a way to help students manage their stressful condition well in order to prevent the damaging effects of stress on the health of students in the University.

Implications for Future Research

The current study is, directly and indirectly, having an impact on the promotion of health and wellbeing among students. The research study was able to provide important information about the psychological state of students during the study period at the University. The study was able to provide detailed evidence to the relationship between stress and depression challenges among females and males in the University. There is a need to implement healthcare facilities and supports for students during their academic periods in order to ensure their safety and wellbeing. Future researchers should focus on studying the major and effective ways that can be used to enhance social support levels among students in the University, designing strategies on campus to make easy contacts between students and clinical psychologists, and other health consultants. This will help improve the well-being of students in the University and enhance their psychological wellness.

Limitations of the Research Study

The study incurred some minor challenges, getting participants to fill questionnaires required meeting them physically, some participants did not fill the questionnaire on the same day, this caused a delay in the filling of the questionnaires in order to collect data on time. Also, the use of

a small sample from one hall in the University makes it difficult to generalize the finding to the whole University. The nature of some items on the questionnaire made students less likely to complete entire questions, since it seems very personal to some students. The qualitative structure of the research made it less likely to develop a detailed description about the actual causes of stress among the students in the University.

Conclusion

Stress and depression are common related problems affecting young adults especially at the tertiary level of education, a country like Ghana is not having high priority to the psychological state and wellbeing of individuals in the country. The study conducted on the association between stress and depression among students in the University showed how severe some students are experiencing psychological problems. The high level of stress among students in the University is linked to several causing factors including the disregard of the country's health facilities among students at the university level. It can be concluded that stress is encountered day-in-day-out, but the proper management of stress especially among students and young adults will help reduce the negative consequences of stress. When students experience stress, they can easily develop other health related problems like depression. The availability of social support to students and young adults will serve a great deal in helping them cope with stress well and manage their health in an effort towards reduction of depression and other health challenges in the future.

REFERENCES

- Anyan, F., & Hjemdal, O. (2016). Adolescent stress and symptoms of anxiety and depression: Resilience explains and differentiates the relationships. *Journal of Affective Disorders, 203*, 213-220.
- Bartolomucci, A., Palanza, P., Sacerdote, P., Panerai, A. E., Sgoifo, A., Dantzer, R., & Parmigiani, S. (2005). Social factors and individual vulnerability to chronic stress exposure. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews, 67-81*. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0149763404001526>
- Bremner, J. D., & Vermetten, E. (2001). *Stress and development: Behavioral and biological consequences*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Retrieved from https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/44868367/Bremner_J._D._Vermetten_E._Stress_and_d20160418-13682-1yvuu2x4.pdf?1461021229=&response-content-disposition=inline%3B+filename%3DStress_and_development_Behavioral_and_bi.pdf&Expires=1615201362&Signature=O2Mwf
- Das, P. P., & Sahoo, R. (2012, July). Stress and Depression among Post Graduate Students. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, 2(7)*, 1-5. Retrieved from <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.440.1578&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- Ellis, A. (1987). A sadly neglected cognitive element in depression. *Cognitive Therapy and Research, 11(1)*, 121-145.
- Felsten, G. (2007). Gender and coping: Use of distinct strategies and associations with stress and depression. *Anxiety, Stress, & Coping Journal, 11(4)*, 289-309. Retrieved from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/10615809808248316>
- Fox, H. C., & Sinha, R. (2009). Sex Differences in Drug-Related Stress-System Changes: Implications for Treatment in Substance-Abusing Women. *Harv Rev Psychiatry, 103-119*. Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2746371/>
- Glozah, N. F. (2013). Effects of Academic Stress and Perceived Social Support on the Psychological Wellbeing of Adolescents in Ghana. *Open Journal of Medical Psychology, 2(4)*, 143-150.
- Gore, S., Aseltine, R. H., & Colten, M. E. (1993). Gender, Social-Relationship Involvement, and Depression. *Journal of Research on Adolescence, 101-125*. Retrieved from https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1207/s15327795jra0302_1
- Hou, F., Bi, F., Jiao, R., Lou, D., & Song, K. (2020). Gender differences of depression and anxiety among social media users during the COVID-19 outbreak in China: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Public Health, 1648*.

- Ingram, R. E., & Luxton, D. D. (2005). Vulnerability-stress models. *Development of psychopathology: A vulnerability-stress perspective*, 46, 32-36. Retrieved from https://us.corwin.com/sites/default/files/upm-binaries/5348_Hankin_Final_pdf_Chapter_2.pdf
- Kessler, R. C., Price, R. H., & Wortman, C. B. (1985). SOCIAL FACTORS IN PSYCHOPATHOLOGY: Stress, Social Support, and Coping Processes. *Psychological Review*, 531-572. Retrieved from <https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/pdf/10.1146/annurev.ps.36.020185.002531>
- Matud, M. P. (2004, November). Gender differences in stress and coping styles. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 37(7), 1401-1415. Retrieved from https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0191886904000200?casa_token=SSSrIv_XIfMAAAAA:KWIBjM3HbiyuUC7t9OyNy3LdqLeri_XOMm88qD0b8yP-uUDIOJScfJvOxWtAangjT9zp-hhPcw
- Monroe, S. M., & Reid, M. W. (2009). Life Stress and Major Depression. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 68-72. Retrieved from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1111/j.1467-8721.2009.01611.x>
- Morgan, P., Dell'Isola, R., Nicholson, B., & Spencer, C. (2020). Stress generation theory in couples with depression: A latent profile analysis. *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships*, 37(7), 2205-2228. Retrieved from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0265407520919992>
- Neumark-Sztainer, D., Story, M., French, S. A., & Resnick, M. D. (1997). Psychosocial correlates of health compromising behaviors among adolescentS. *Health Education Research*, 37-52. Retrieved from <https://academic.oup.com/her/article/12/1/37/811337?login=true>
- O'Connor, D. B., Thayer, J. F., & Vedhara, K. (2021). Stress and Health: A Review of Psychobiological Processes. *Annual Review of Psychology Journal*, 663-688. Retrieved from <https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/full/10.1146/annurev-psych-062520-122331>
- Palgi, Y., & Dicker-Oren, S. D. (2020). Evaluating a community fire as human-made vs. natural disaster moderates teh relationship between peritraumatic distress and both PTSD symptoms and posttraumatic growth. *Anxiety, Stress & Coping Journal*, 569-580. Retrieved from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/10615806.2020.1755818>
- Ptacek, J. T., Smith, R. E., & Dodge, K. L. (1994). Gender Differences in Coping with Stress: When Stressor and Appraisals Do Not Differ. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 421-430. Retrieved from

- <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0146167294204009#articleCitationDownloadContainer>
- Saleh, D., Camart, N., & Romo, L. (2017, January 25). *Predictors of Stress in College Students*. Retrieved from Frontiers :
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00019/full>
- Schneiderman, N., Ironson, G., & Siegel, S. D. (2005). STRESS AND HEALTH: Psychological, Behavioral, and Biological Determinants. *HHS Author Manuscripts*, 607-628. Retrieved from NCBI: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2568977/>
- Sigmon, S. T., Pells, J. J., Schartel, J. G., Hermann, B. A., Edenfield, T. M., LaMattina, S. M., . . . Whitcomb-Smith, S. R. (2007, May). Stress reactivity and coping in seasonal and nonseasonal depression. *Behaviour Research and Therapy*, 45(5), 965-975. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0005796706001677>
- Simantov, E., Schoen, C., & Klein, J. D. (2000). Health-Compromising Behaviors: Why Do Adolescents Smoke or Drink? Identifying Underlying Risk and Protective Factors. *Arch Pediatr Adolesc Med*, 1025-1033. Retrieved from <https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jamapediatrics/article-abstract/351569>
- Skipworth, K. (2011). Relationship between perceived stress and depression in college students. (*Doctoral dissertation, Arizona State University*), 33-45.
- Thoits, P. A. (1999). Sociological approaches to mental illness. In A. F. Horwitz, & T. L. Scheid (Eds.), *A handbook for the study of mental health: Social contexts, theories, and systems* (pp. 121-138). Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Tiller, J. W. (2013). Depression and anxiety. *The Medical Journal of Australia*, 199(6), 28-31. Retrieved from https://www.mja.com.au/journal/2013/199/6/depression-and-anxiety?fbclid=IwAR1kDPMjhnRi24XcknQYgsyBix71Y_PVLF83XxCBOXFFX6vyXFfahm1RxmQ
- Wege, N., Li, J., & Siegrist, J. (2018). Are their gender differences in associations of effort–reward imbalance at work with self-reported doctor-diagnosed depression? Prospective evidence from the German Socio-Economic Panel. *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*, 435-443. Retrieved from <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00420-018-1293-8>
- Weigel, D. J., & Shrout, M. R. (2020). Relational turbulence and health-compromising behaviors: Integrating relational turbulence and stress theories. *Journal of the International Association for Relationship Research*, 785-800. Retrieved from https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/per.12347?casa_token=tFDqJBt_S-

IAAAAA%3AMa5z6RRy61TdMWYvedmLaF8sVEXIDxBMx-
GjXNNjfO4IYJeXURE37FXMUbKIZ2Bauua9vx00sMyFSIA

- Yang, L., Zhao, Y., Wang, Y., Lio, L., Zhang, X., Li, B., & Cui, R. (2015). The Effects of Psychological Stress on Depression. *Current Neuropharmacology Journal*, 494-504. Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4790405/>
- Yehuda, R. (1999). Biological Factors Associated with Susceptibility to Posttraumatic Stress Disorder. *The Canadian Journal of Psychiatry*, 34-39. Retrieved from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/070674379904400104>

APPENDICES**ASSOCIATIONS BETWEEN LEVEL OF STRESS AND DEPRESSION AMONG STUDENTS****Appendix A**

Dear Participant,

I am a final year undergraduate student from the Department of Psychology at the University of Ghana, Legon. I would be very grateful if you could spend some few minutes to complete this questionnaire. The purpose of the research is to understand the association between level of stress and depression among students of the University of Ghana, with a focus towards undergraduate students in the Legon Hall of the University of Ghana. You are not obliged to write your name on the questionnaire. Participation in this research is voluntary and confidentially assured. **THIS IS NOT A TEST. PLEASE PROVIDE HONEST RESPONSES AS MUCH AS POSSIBLE.** Thank you for your interest in participating in this study. Please tick/fill all responses, and feel free to contact me on jmahati@st.ug.edu.gh regarding this research.

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

1. What is your age?
2. What is your gender
 - a. Male
 - b. Female
3. Marital Status:
 - a. Married
 - b. Single
 - c. Divorced
 - d. Have a regular /study sexual partner
 - e. Have casual sexual relationships
 - f. Other (please specify)
4. What is your religious affiliation:

- a. Christian (Orthodox)
 - b. Christian (Pentecostal)
 - c. Christian (Charismatic)
 - e. Moslem
 - f. Traditionalist
 - g. Other (Specify)
5. Programme of Study?
6. Level
- a. 100
 - b. 200
 - c. 300
 - d. 400
7. What extracurricular activities are you part of?
- a. Sport
 - b. Singing
 - c. Student Leadership
 - d. Other, please state

Appendix B

Perceived Stress Scale

Please answer the following questions on individual personal stress levels. This will help measure the level of stress during the last month. Some questions may look similar but there are differences between them and must be treated as separate questions. Indicate your level of agreement (using a scoring ranging from 0-4) to the following sentences by filling the spaces below.

0= Never, 1= almost never, 2= Sometimes, 3= fairly often, 4= very often

_____ 1. In the last month, how often have you been upset because of something that happened unexpectedly?

_____ 2. In the last month, how often have you felt that you were unable to control the important things in your life?

_____ 3. In the last month, how often have you felt nervous and stressed?

_____ 4. In the last month, how often have you felt confident about your ability to handle your personal problems?

_____ 5. In the last month, how often have you felt that things were going your way?

_____ 6. In the last month, how often have you found that you could not cope with all the things that you had to do?

_____ 7. In the last month, how often have you been able to control irritations in your life?

_____ 8. In the last month, how often have you felt that you were on top of things?

_____ 9. In the last month, how often have you been angered because of things that happened that were outside of your control?

_____ 10. In the last month, how often have you felt difficulties were piling up so high that you could not overcome them?

Appendix C

Beck's Depression Inventory

Please answer the following questions by ticking the one that applies to you the most, the range is from 0-3 depending on the level of your agreement. This depression scale can be self-scored.

1.

- 0 I do not feel sad.
- 1 I feel sad
- 2 I am sad all the time and I can't snap out of it.
- 3 I am so sad and unhappy that I can't stand it.

2.

- 0 I am not particularly discouraged about the future.
- 1 I feel discouraged about the future.
- 2 I feel I have nothing to look forward to.
- 3 I feel the future is hopeless and that things cannot improve.

3.

- 0 I do not feel like a failure.
- 1 I feel I have failed more than the average person.

- 2 As I look back on my life, all I can see is a lot of failures.
3 I feel I am a complete failure as a person.
4. 0 I get as much satisfaction out of things as I used to.
1 I don't enjoy things the way I used to.
2 I don't get real satisfaction out of anything anymore.
3 I am dissatisfied or bored with everything.
5. 0 I don't feel particularly guilty
1 I feel guilty a good part of the time.
2 I feel quite guilty most of the time.
3 I feel guilty all of the time.
6. 0 I don't feel I am being punished.
1 I feel I may be punished.
2 I expect to be punished.
3 I feel I am being punished.
7. 0 I don't feel disappointed in myself.
1 I am disappointed in myself.
2 I am disgusted with myself.
3 I hate myself.
8. 0 I don't feel I am any worse than anybody else.
1 I am critical of myself for my weaknesses or mistakes.
2 I blame myself all the time for my faults.
3 I blame myself for everything bad that happens.
9. 0 I don't have any thoughts of killing myself.
1 I have thoughts of killing myself, but I would not carry them out.
2 I would like to kill myself.
3 I would kill myself if I had the chance.
10. 0 I don't cry any more than usual.
1 I cry more now than I used to.
2 I cry all the time now.
3 I used to be able to cry, but now I can't cry even though I want to.
11. 0 I am no more irritated by things than I ever was.
1 I am slightly more irritated now than usual.
2 I am quite annoyed or irritated a good deal of the time.
3 I feel irritated all the time.
12. 0 I have not lost interest in other people.
1 I am less interested in other people than I used to be.
2 I have lost most of my interest in other people.

13. 3 I have lost all of my interest in other people.
0 I make decisions about as well as I ever could.
1 I put off making decisions more than I used to.
2 I have greater difficulty in making decisions more than I used to.
3 I can't make decisions at all anymore.
14. 0 I don't feel that I look any worse than I used to.
1 I am worried that I am looking old or unattractive.
2 I feel there are permanent changes in my appearance that make me look unattractive
3 I believe that I look ugly.
15. 0 I can work about as well as before.
1 It takes an extra effort to get started at doing something.
2 I have to push myself very hard to do anything.
3 I can't do any work at all.
16. 0 I can sleep as well as usual.
1 I don't sleep as well as I used to.
2 I wake up 1-2 hours earlier than usual and find it hard to get back to sleep.
3 I wake up several hours earlier than I used to and cannot get back to sleep.
17. 0 I don't get more tired than usual.
1 I get tired more easily than I used to.
2 I get tired from doing almost anything.
3 I am too tired to do anything.
18. 0 My appetite is no worse than usual.
1 My appetite is not as good as it used to be.
2 My appetite is much worse now.
3 I have no appetite at all anymore.
19. 0 I haven't lost much weight, if any, lately.
1 I have lost more than five pounds.
2 I have lost more than ten pounds.
3 I have lost more than fifteen pounds. 20.
20. 0 I am no more worried about my health than usual.
1 I am worried about physical problems like aches, pains, upset stomach, or constipation.
2 I am very worried about physical problems and it's hard to think of much else.
3 I am so worried about my physical problems that I cannot think of anything else.
- 21.

- 0 I have not noticed any recent change in my interest in sex.
- 1 I am less interested in sex than I used to be.
- 2 I have almost no interest in sex.
- 3 I have lost interest in sex completely.

Appendix D

Social Support Scale

This part of the Social Support Scale is made up of a list of appraisal support statements each of which may or may not be true about you. For each statement, tick "definitely true" if you are sure, it is true about you and "probably true" if you think it is true but are not absolutely certain. Similarly, you should tick "definitely false" if you are sure the statement is false and "probably false" if you think it is false but are not absolutely certain.

- 1. I feel that there is no one I can share my most private worries and fears with.
 - 1. definitely false
 - 2. probably false
 - 3. probably true
 - 4. definitely true
- 2. There is someone I can turn to for advice about handling problems with my family.
 - 1. definitely false
 - 2. probably false
 - 3. probably true
 - 4. definitely true
- 3. When I need suggestions on how to deal with a personal problem, I know someone I can turn to.
 - 1. definitely false
 - 2. probably false
 - 3. probably true
 - 4. definitely true
- 11. If a family crisis arose, it would be difficult to find someone who could give me good advice about how to handle it.
 - 1. definitely false
 - 2. probably false
 - 3. probably true
 - 4. definitely true

Thank you very much for the time spent in filling this questionnaire and your willingness to share quite personal information with me. Once again, I am grateful.